

Development of the labour migration management system

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the challenges of labour migration which must be solved by our state, society and the migrants themselves. Labour migration is one of the most important issues of population and it must be considered not only in terms of simple mechanical people flow but as complex social process which relates to different aspects of socio-economic life, and this fact makes such challenges especially up-to-date. Migration of labour resources is a creative economic and social power leading to development of economy, enrichment of cultures and inflow of workforce. The article provides analysis of the situation with migrants in our country and positive and negative consequences of labour migration for sending and receiving countries. Basic adaptation strategies used by migrants are considered.*

Key words: labour resources, migration, adaptation, migration processes, mobility of workforce, labour potential, workers.

Processes which take place in modern socio-cultural space are key element of changes in social, economic and cultural spheres of society. Migration process influences changes of spatial social relationship both negatively and positively [1-4]. Under the influence of globalization the number of forms of migration in the world has increased. All these forms can not be regarded separately because one form can be transformed into the other depending on specific motives and conditions [5]. No doubts that labour process needs proper organization, not only for getting economic effect but for man's development as well [6].

Labour migration is one of the important questions of population and it must be considered not only in terms of simple mechanical people flow but as complex social process which relates to different aspects of socio-economic life, and this fact makes such challenges especially up-to-date[11].

At the boundary between XX - XXI centuries Russia like other countries faced great inflow of migrants which was the effect of new political and socio-cultural situation: disintegration of the USSR, intense globalization processes.

It is surprising but migration policy often considers labour migration in narrow-economic aspect: either as a source of workforce or as compensation of natural increase of population. Thus, the authorities do not strive to balance the interests of the state, society, business and the migrants themselves, proposed institutional and regulatory mechanisms are insufficient for solution of existing problems.

Of course, absence of social costs allows to save much money of Russian employers thanks to temporal labour migrants: otherwise these employers would incur such costs for Russian workforce.

Being a part of socio-economic policy it performs structuring function - ties up the project of socio-economic development with the project (forecast) of quantity, quality and distribution of population.

Attraction of workforce from other countries into Russia and integration of migrants can be fulfilled in conditions of intact socio-cultural nucleus of our society. Maximization of profit from migration must be compared with social risks associated with this phenomenon and the search for the tools of efficient interaction between exporting and importing countries must be done with due regard to mutually beneficial interests and harmonization of international migration legislature [8].

State policy in the sphere of employment is aimed for rational distribution of production forces, higher mobility of labour resources with due regard to the labour market and its perspective needs. One of the most important measures – aid for refugees and forced migrants to adapt themselves, regulation of labour migration flows.

In the same time labour migration has both positive and negative features. It reduces labour costs in receiving country; on the contrary, the costs of labour in sending country go up, employment in the receiving country increases while in sending country it decreases, local population is pushed out from labour market (Table 1). While forming migration policy all the consequences of labour migration must be taken into consideration in order to make this process more beneficial for both parties and decrease the number of negative moments [7].

Table 1
Key effects of labour migration for sending and receiving countries.

Receiving country		Sending country	
<i>Positive effects</i>	<i>Negative effects</i>	<i>Positive effects</i>	<i>Negative effects</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reduction of costs for training of new workers and specialists; - higher competitiveness' of products because of lower production costs of foreign workforce; - foreign workers can be easily dismissed; - saving money thanks to pensions and other social pay-offs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - deterioration of local labour market; -reduction of labour wages because the labour demand increases; -illegal immigration and criminality growth; - factor of social tension. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - less tension in internal labour market; - growth of population well-being thanks to money transfers of migrants; - improvement of poverty level; - less load on the budget: no unemployment pay-offs etc.; - opportunity to have more qualified workforce after returning of migrants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - loss of a part of labour resources at active age; - state does not get return from costs of education and professional training of its citizens; - brain drain; -deterioration of family relations.

Russia while participating in labour migration is both receiving and sending party, that is why its national migration policy is oriented to realization of multi-sided purposes and is built in accordance with tasks of global world, added by super-national regulation (Table 1).

Mass migration and emigration in Russian Federation have resulted in different variants of interaction with receiving party. Such situation raises the problem of socio-cultural adaptation of different ethnic groups.

Socio-cultural adaptation can be defined as a process and the result of active adjustment of ethnic groups to conditions of other socio-cultural environment. The importance of socio-cultural adaptation in other ethnic environment is determined by objective contradiction between internationalized ethnic cultural frame, habitual needs, interests of migrants, settled model of their social activity (group ethnic identity of migrants and new social conditions of their life activity, their changed status (identity of receiving community) [9].

4 basic strategies used by migrants in the process of adaptation are as follows: (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Basic strategies used by migrants for adaptation

Every strategy has its own features:

1. Strategy of passive autarchy suggests that migrants avoid direct contacts with foreign culture and eliminate negative symptoms of cultural shock. This strategy is used by representatives of ethnic minorities (forced migrants and refugees) living in big cities, city conglomerates.
2. The strategy of aggressive autarchy is when the other culture is bitterly criticized and refused and the migrants are actively striving to implement their own cultural attributes and stereotypes into new environment, to dictate their own world view to the environment.
3. The strategy of assimilation suggests voluntary or forced refusal of migrants from native culture and complete absorption by new ethnos.
4. Strategy of integration is one of the most successful strategies of adaptation when ethnic minorities keep devotion to their culture. Activization of intercultural dialogue between migrants and dominating ethnic majority takes place.

Choice of some strategy depends on the whole range of factors:

- 1) personal characteristics (age, the level of education, values, motivation). Values, values orientations - the attitude of personality to social values which regulate its behaviour [10].
- 2) characteristics of interacting cultures (objectively existing and subjectively perceived the degree of similarity or difference between the cultures).

Conclusions. Absence of conditions for intake and distribution of migrants often prevents from giving work to labour migrants.

It should be mentioned that policy in the sphere of labour migration in Russia is not sufficiently elaborated and must be changed greatly not only on regional but on federal level.

Indeed, for development of economy, society and human potential we need efficient labour migration management system.

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